

Research in *Ginkgo biloba* : Recent developments

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This article depicts the present state of research in *Ginkgo biloba* L. Firstly, cognizance has been taken that *G. biloba* living plants and fossils (30 to 200 million year old) are distributed all over India. The species may have an Indian name and identity. Secondly, extensive ecological and seasonal variations in the secondary metabolites of *G. biloba* have been observed. There is, therefore, a need for proper standardization of Ginkgo extracts used for therapeutic purposes. The existing 'standardized' extracts, including EGb-761, are not truly standardized. EGb-761 itself accounts for only 30% of the contained ingredients. Thirdly, the major therapeutic effects, e.g. anti-PAF (platelet activating factor) and the attendant biological actions, solely attributed to ginkgolide-B, in earlier reports, have now been found to be due also to other constituents entrapped within the cage of ginkgolide-B. Fourthly, forskolin, a potent anti-PAF factor, has been found to occur in EGb-761 as also within the cage of ginkgolide-B. This provides rationalization to a number of earlier detected inexplicable phenomena with Ginkgo extracts. The other constituents found within the cage of the 'claimed' analytically pure samples of ginkgolide-B (obtained from authentic sources) are ginkgolic acid conjugates (GACs), catechins/procyanidins and flavonols. Finally, the clue to the longevity and virility of *G. biloba* (it starts reproducing from 16 years and continues to do so up to 1000 years) has been located in Ginkgo fossils, which retain a number of systemic acquired resistance (SAR)-inducers, e.g. GACs and terpenic lactones.

I am beholden to the Indian Chemical Society for electing me to deliver the Professor P. K. Bose Memorial Lecture. Professor Bose, a doyen among natural product chemists in India, during his four decades of research since 1934, enriched our knowledge and understanding of the chemistry of a vast body of natural compounds including coumarins, flavonoids, bitter furanoids and nitrogen heterocycles. Many among these compounds have been included as phytopharmaceuticals.

Phytomedicines today occupy a very important position worldwide in human healthcare systems. The world populace whether to stave-off disease, to seek to brighten their moods, to rewin their sex lives or retain their youth are in-

creasingly replacing their prescription medicines (allopathic) with herbal remedies. As a consequence, the fast growing commercial interest in herbal medicines has pushed off serious effort in natural product research to backtrack to meet the growing demand for phytomedicines. *G. biloba* is a glaring example of this laxity and bears many grey areas.

The background

Ginkgo biloba L., the oldest phytotherapeutic agent known to mankind, is also known as maidenhair tree (for its delicate fern-like foliage and shape of the lamina), or the 'living fossil', as herbalists fondly call it. *G. biloba* is the only living species of the family Ginkgoaceae whose fossil also co-exists. Its ancestry dates back to the Jurassic and Cretaceous eras (some 200 million years ago)¹. Ginkgo was mentioned in the Chinese pharmacopoeia (2800 B.C.) for its many therapeutic uses². Surprisingly, a recent report³ from the West mentions it as the 'Soma' (elixir or life) of Ayurveda. Indeed, some characteristic changes in young Ginkgo plants after first spring-flush, e.g. yellowing and fall of each of 15 leaves synchronized with the lunar cycle, and the 'cure-all' properties of the leaf-extracts, satisfy the descriptions of 'Soma' of Ayurveda⁴. Furthermore, Ginkgo fossils (30 to 200 million year-old) have been located in many parts of India. Its leaf part was excavated from the Triassic formation of the South Rewa Gondwana Basin⁵; from formation of Sher river, Jabalpur⁵. Its fossil trunks were found at the Rajmahal Hills, Bihar, in the upper Gondwanas outlying the Madras Coast, in Ooty, and in the fossil garden, Barmer, Rajasthan⁶. It is, therefore, surprising that there is no Indian synonym of Ginkgo in the Indian Botanical treatise. Many Indian chemists also are not aware that India too is a rich store-house of living *G. biloba* and its fossil.

The survival feat of *Ginkgo biloba* :

Several members of the Ginkgoales occupied the surface of the earth 200 million years before present time. With the passage of time all other members except *G. biloba* became extinct. *G. biloba* has survived for several million years of challenging geological and chemical onslaughts including ice age and catastrophic extinctions of most of the ex-

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tant species. *G. biloba* is one of the very few living organisms that survived the man's most destructive act – the nuclear bombing at Hiroshima. The tree of *G. biloba* that re-emerged after the devastation, did not show any chromosomal mutation induced by the atomic radiation. The stubborn resistance of *G. biloba* to all forms of relentless stress, including pests and disease-causing fungi, bacteria and viruses, is indeed amazing. Its combating factors (*vide infra*) are, in fact, augmented in response to different forms of stress. Its viri-lity is also a unique feature. Ginkgo tree starts reproducing at the age of 16 years and continue to do so for more than 1000 years.

G. biloba in commerce :

It is included in modern Chinese pharmacopoeia as an antiasthmatic and antitussive phytomedicine⁷. In Europe, Ginkgo formulations were introduced into market during the nineteensixties. The foremost among the formulations is the 'standardized extract' of *G. biloba*, named EGb-761 (Extractum Ginkgo bilobae-761), co-developed by messers Willmar Schwabe, Ipsen and Intersan. Various products, made from EGb-761 and other *G. biloba* leaf-extracts are now available all over the world. Some of these are Rokan[®], Ginkoba[®], Kaveri[®], Tanakan[®] and Tebokan[®]. EGb-761 has also entered into Indian market. Some of the products, purported to be prepared from EGb-761 and other extracts of *G. biloba* are Ginkocer, Bilovas, Geritisin and Ginkomeckel. *G. biloba* products have an estimated worldwide annual sale of nearly 4 billion US dollars, and its market is ever increasing⁸.

Clinical indications :

Ginkgo therapy is recommended in disorders of peripheral blood circulation, in alleviating cerebrovascular dysfunctions, in bronchial asthma, in cardiovascular disorders, as adjuvant treatment of cerebral ischaemia and in geriatric complaints^{3,8,13,17}.

Standardization of Ginkgo :

In spite of the enviable reputation and extremely lucrative market, no serious attempt has been made earlier to develop a well-defined quality control of the commercial Ginkgo extracts, including EGb-761⁹. Rather, it seems to be a deliberate marketing strategy not to project the rigorous quality control standards of Ginkgo because the species exhibits marked ecological and seasonal variations of its bioactive constituents.

Present study

Several commercial Ginkgo formulation/products have been found to suffer from marked fluctuations in the contents of Ginkgo bioactive constituents, e.g. the terpenic lac-

tones, ginkgolide-B (Fig. 1, 1), bilobalide (2), forskolin (3) and the lipoidal compounds (ginkgolic acids conjugates, GACs) (4). Even EGb-761 is only a partially defined (to

Fig. 1. Metabolites of living and fossil *G. biloba*.

the extent of 30%) product. It is standardized on the contents of Ginkgo flavonoid glycosides (rel. abundance, 24%) and the terpenic lactones (ginkgolide-B and bilobalide, 6%). Several other preparations, e.g. Kaveri, Ginkosan, Craton, produced in a similar way as EGb-761, are standardized in respect of only the flavonoid glycosides contents (16–25%, w/w). The scenario is more bleak in India. Ginkgo products purported to be prepared from EGb-761 are defined only in terms of flavonoid glycosides (of fluctuating abundance); the manufacturers are silent about the contents of the terpenic lactones, since these are either absent or occur only in traces. We have used comprehensive chromatographic analyses (HPTLC and HPLC) using authentic markers to establish these points. Besides the terpenic lactones and the flavonoid glycosides, there are several other potent bioactive compounds (*vide infra*) that contribute to the clinical efficacy of *G. biloba* extracts. Manufacturers carefully shun these constituents for several reasons. Considerable fluctuations and even absence of these constituents have been observed in several of the marketed formulations of Ginkgo. For instance, Ginkgo leaves contain procyanidins¹⁰, ginkgolic acids (= 6-alkylsalicylic and 4-hydroxy-6-alkylsalicylic acids)¹¹, ginkgolic acid conjugates (*O*-alkyl, *O*-acyl phospholipid conjugates which we named 'Ginkgosomes')¹², and phenolic acids and conjugated phytosteroids¹³. These compounds also contribute to the therapeutic effects of Ginkgo. Commercial houses harvest Ginkgo leaves from different places but only once, at the time of maturity of the leaves. Since marked

ecological and seasonal variations in the secondary metabolites of *Ginkgo* are observed, most of the marketed samples of *Ginkgo* formulations suffer from one or more of the abovementioned deficiencies in their standard.

Seasonal and ontogenic variations of *Ginkgo* metabolites :

Very little work in this direction was carried out before¹⁴. We have investigated the chemical constituents of *G. biloba* leaves from 1-, 2-, 3-, 5-, 10-, 30-, 60-, 80- and 120-year-old plants/trees, collected at 15-day interval during the complete vegetative cycle (end of April to end of October) for five consecutive years. The general method of extraction is depicted in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1. General method of solvent-gradient extraction of *G. biloba* (leaves).

The chloroform-, acetone-, and methanol-extractives (Scheme 1) were subjected to comprehensive chromatographic (HPTLC, HPLC) and spectroscopic (FT-IR, 300 MHz, ¹H NMR and GC-MS) (as silyl derivatives) analy-

ses. Distinct waxing and waning patterns in the relative abundance of the bioactive constituents were discerned in the samples collected at different periods of vegetation (seasonal variation) (Fig. 2). Interestingly, only marginal effect of the age of the plant was reflected on the chemical constituents of leaves. Thus, *G. biloba* does not exhibit any significant ontogenic variation in its secondary metabolites, which is yet another unique feature of *Ginkgo*.

New bioactive constituents :

In addition to the earlier reported¹³ bioactive constituents, we have isolated two more new groups of bioactive compounds, viz. forskolin (and related labdane diterpenes, e.g. manool) (Fig. 1, 3) and ginkgolic acid conjugates (ginkgosomes) (4) from *Ginkgo* leaves as also from EGb-761.

Forskolin (3): This diterpene was earlier reported from the roots of *Coleus forskolii*¹⁵. This is the second source (*Ginkgo*) of forskolin in nature. Forskolin directly activates adenylate cyclase in membrane preparations and in intact cells from a variety of tissues. It augments receptor-mediated increase in cyclic-AMP. The physiological response of forskolin in human platelets, which is linked to the activation of c-AMP systems, is inhibition of aggression¹⁶. Additionally, the c-AMP-independent action of forskolin results in intraocular pressure lowering and cardiotoxic properties. Hence, the occurrence of forskolin in *G. biloba* and its presence in EGb-761 have now raised serious question whether the anti-PAF and allied effects^{3,13,17} of *G. biloba* extracts are exclusively due to ginkgolide-B, or are to be attributed, also to forskolin. In view of this observation, it is worthwhile to consider a unique structural characteristic of ginkgolide-B.

Ginkgolide-B as cage molecule: Ginkgolide-B samples (initially obtained from Dr. Willmar Schwabe GmbH (WS) and through the courtesy of Professor Braquet (Ipsen)) were all found to contain several other constituents of *G. biloba*.

Fig. 2. Seasonal variations of bioactive constituents of *G. biloba* : (x) ginkgolic acid, (O) forskolin, (□) phospholipids, (Δ) ginkgolide-B.

of application in chemistry and biology²¹. The lipophilic long-chain alkyl/alkenyl groups of ginkgolic acids have a propensity to form molecular laminates and other organized structures. The selective ionophoric properties of the 6-alkyl/alkenyl salicylates are of particular interest in view of their possible role in the metabolic processes and longevity (of Ginkgo) of the producer and other interacted organisms. Such lipophilic complexes containing iron and zinc ions have been detected in Marc-C (Scheme 1).

Ginkgo fossil :

Quite in contrast to its very recent confinement, in the wild state, to a limited area in China, Ginkgo trees formerly ranged far and wide over the surface of the earth. Hence, the widely distributed record of fossil of Ginkgo is not unexpected. The significant aspect is the chemical evaluation of the fossils and the resultant detection of ginkgolic acids, bilobalide and forskolin in them¹⁹. This observation would seem to provide the clue to the longevity of Ginkgo. Salicylic acid and equivalents (SAs), and certain terpenoids are known to combat different forms of stress (both static and dynamic) by producing disease-resistant protein²². The SAs are widely distributed in plant kingdom albeit in varying amounts. While the healing properties of salicylates have been known since antiquity, the function of SAs in living plants was discovered only a few years ago. Several lines of evidence indicate that endogenous SAs are a signal molecule in SAR (Systemic Acquired Resistance) in plants²². Jasmonic acid (JA) and methyljasmonate (Me-JA) are two naturally occurring acetogenins which were implicated in wound-activated endogenous signals that may alert undamaged tissues of producer and neighboring plants of an impending stress phenomenon^{19,22}. The protective role of the GACs and the terpenes in Ginkgo would, therefore, seem to contribute to the longevity and health of Ginkgo plants and also for the preservation of its fossil on the surface of the earth.

Conclusion :

Contrary to earlier belief of some Indian chemists (their personal communication with the author), living trees and fossils (of different age-groups) of *G. biloba* co-occur in many parts of India. One would like to know the Indian synonym of Ginkgo (Chinese scholars say that the word Ginkgo means *hill apricot*, in appearance Ginkgo fruit looks like an apricot). Ginkgo appears as a slender tree at the initial stage of ontogeny – a slow growing plant for the first two decades or so of its life. We do not know if 'Soma' of Ayurveda is a true Ginkgo or a Ginkgo progenitor, but the young Ginkgo plant exhibits certain characteristics which

are similar to those described for 'Soma' in the Ayurvedic literature. The elixir effect of Ginkgo is consonant with that of Soma.

Although not much ontogenic (age of plants) variations, in respect of the bioactive constituents of Ginkgo, were observed, their marked seasonal variations point to the need of true standardization of Ginkgo extracts used for therapeutic purposes. The collection of Ginkgo leaves only once, at the time of maturity, for commercial purpose poses a serious limitation as to the quality of Ginkgo medicines. In view of this, the occurrence of GACs and forskolin in EGb-761 assumes marked significance. This is further supported by the detection of GACs and forskolin in Ginkgo fossil, which offers an explanation in respect of the chemical protectors. Proper standardization of Ginkgo extracts and formulations is thus an imperative necessity. A situation is now prevailing when the entire R & D in commercial houses dealing with natural medicines is driven by market forces. This does not auger well for the future of natural medicines and for the world populace. This would, by no means, belittle the high quality research on natural products now being carried out in scientific research laboratories all over the world. The fact is, that the informations generated are not marshalled in commercial practice. India, the land of natural medicines, cannot afford to remain apathetic to the vast body of information generated in this field. A serious and accountable cohesive effort in this direction is warranted.

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